

nextGEMS

Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems

Deliverable title	Final report on exploitation, incl. plan for post nextGEMS era
Deliverable number	D51 (Del. Rel. No. D1.9)
Planned delivery date	31/07/2025
Actual date of issue	31/07/2025
Nature of deliverable	Report
Lead partner	MPI-M
Dissemination level	Public

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

About this document

Summary of the implementation on exploitation activities and exploitation plan beyond project lifetime.

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WP1

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Executive summary

This report outlines how the results of the Horizon 2020 project *nextGEMS* are being exploited beyond the project's runtime. It focuses on three main outputs: storm-resolving Earth system model development, high-resolution simulation datasets, and scientific publications. These results are already reused across scientific, technical, and institutional settings, through successor projects, open data access, and educational activities.

The report identifies key target groups—ranging from model developers and applied users to technologists, policy actors, and the public—and describes how they benefit from and contribute to the uptake of project results. It also details concrete exploitation measures, including integration into institutional workflows, training formats, and strategic communication efforts that ensure long-term impact.

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Objectives

Project objectives

This deliverable contributes to the achievement of the following specific project topics.

The table below outlines the overarching objectives of the nextGEMS. Objectives that the work for the current deliverable contributes to are marked with *yes*.

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
O1	
To develop two SR-ESMs for applications	
(i) by demonstrating their capacity to more realistically represent the coupled (land-ocean-atmosphere) climate system, also through an ability to better leverage observations;	no
(ii) by performing the first global multi-decadal (30 y) SR-ESM based climate projections, testing for out-of-sample climate trajectories, i.e., surprises, and thereby giving a new perspective on uncertainty; and	no
(iii) by expanding their scope to begin more physically coupling 'Earth-system' processes, including the carbon cycle and the atmospheric aerosol	no
O2	
To use SR-ESMs to test emerging and long-standing hypotheses underpinning our understanding of climate change:	
(i) that convective organization contributes importantly to Earth's energy budget and the strength of cloud feedbacks;	no
(ii) that a more explicit representation of cloud-aerosol interactions mutes aerosol-radiative forcing;	no
(iii) that 2 km to 200 km scale atmospheric and oceanic circulations are of leading order importance for air-sea fluxes in the tropics, thereby influencing not only the mean tropical and mid-latitude climate, but also its variability, including extremes;	no

Specific objectives of the project	Contribution of this deliverable?
(iv) that storm-scale variability in weather systems and of the land surface strongly influence extra-tropical climate and extremes, for instance by conditioning circulation regimes, like blocking;	no
(v) that capturing landscape variability globally greatly improves the realism with which regional climate can be simulated; and	no
(vi) that storm-scale variability through its impact on hydrological extremes affects the carbon budget, with associated implications for the global carbon (emissions) stock-take.	no

O3

To build new, more integrated, communities of ESM users by:

- | | |
|--|-----|
| (i) exploiting the necessity of developing SR-ESMs around a centralized infrastructure to create development and analysis paradigms that can more directly involve a broader and more distributed scientific community; and | yes |
| (ii) by exploiting the affinity between what people experience and what SR-ESMs simulate (i.e., events, in addition to statistics) to more directly involve non-scientific users in model development, thereby fostering Knowledge Coproduction. | no |

Work package objectives

This deliverable directly contributes to the achievement of specific objectives indicated in the description of the Work Package as indicated below.

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Day to day project management	yes
Scientific coordination including quality assurance (KPI) and risk assessment	no

Objectives of WP1	Relevance in this deliverable?
Data management	no
Ensure efficient innovation management, managing exploitation of project results	yes
Supporting communication and dissemination activities	yes
Clustering with EC, regional and international projects/programmes	no

Synergies

Synergies Within nextGEMS: The exploitation of results in *nextGEMS* is inherently linked to all work packages, as the development and reuse of storm-resolving Earth system models, simulation datasets, and associated workflows are cross-cutting by nature.

- **WP1 (Coordination)** provided the organizational and strategic backbone for exploitation planning and partner engagement.
- **WP2 and WP3** were central to model development, tuning, and simulation production—the technical foundation for all exploitation activities.
- **WPs 4–9** (Radiation, Ocean, Land, and Application WPs) exploited simulation outputs and diagnostics for process studies, bias evaluation, and stakeholder-relevant analyses.
- **WP10 (Communication and Dissemination)** supported outreach and visibility, enabling exploitation through strategic messaging and communication formats.

The collaborative structures established—such as open hackathons, challenge problem formats, and shared workflows—cut across all work packages and created a common platform for scientific, technical, and stakeholder engagement. These community-based approaches have been adopted both within and beyond the project.

Synergies with Other Projects: *nextGEMS* has strong synergies with several other national and European research projects, enabling knowledge exchange, data reuse, and shared infrastructure development.

- **WarmWorld:** Continues storm-resolving model development, building directly on the technical and scientific outcomes of *nextGEMS*. It inherits simulation setups, diagnostics, and software environments.
- **TerraDT, DestinE:** Integrates high-resolution climate simulations into digital twin frame-

works. It exploits data structures and simulation protocols developed in nextGEMS and uses its outputs as part of test cases and model evaluation.

- **EERIE**: Collaborated with nextGEMS in joint hackathon activities and code development. Shared tooling, intake catalogs, and analysis workflows illustrate an active synergy at the infrastructure and training level.
- **ESM2025**: A parallel project funded under the same call, focusing on Earth system model development and science-policy dialogue. nextGEMS outputs such as the science explainers were integrated into ESM2025's education and communication resources. Both projects were also part of the #ClimateResearchNet communication network, fostering aligned messaging and outreach.

These synergies enhance the visibility, relevance, and long-term usability of nextGEMS outputs and ensure that its legacy is embedded in the evolving European Earth system modeling landscape.

1. Introduction

The *nextGEMS* project (Next Generation Earth Modelling Systems) was launched to pioneer the development and application of storm-resolving Earth system models (SR-ESMs). Over the course of the project, substantial progress was made in advancing model capabilities, generating high-resolution simulation datasets, and engaging diverse stakeholder groups in co-producing and exploiting project outputs.

This final report focuses on the exploitation of project results and outlines the pathways through which the outcomes of *nextGEMS* will be sustained and expanded upon beyond the project's duration. It highlights the key technical and scientific achievements, the main target groups reached, and the concrete measures taken to enable reuse, integration, and further development of the project's outputs. It also identifies links to successor projects, institutional uptake, and strategic communication activities that ensure continued relevance and impact.

2. Exploitation

2.1. Overview of Key Results

The key results of the project are the work on the storm-resolving ESM development, the simulation datasets and scientific publications. More details on each of the results are given below.

Storm-resolving ESM development

Successfully configured ICON and IFS through three iterative cycles (1–3), culminating in robust multi-decadal SR-ESM runs available at 4-5 km resolution (Cycle 3 via DOI above), include also other key achievements:

- **HEALPix hierarchical output:** Model output is written on a HEALPix grid at multiple resolutions—typically a fine level (e.g., $z=10$, 6 km) and coarser levels—allowing users to select data at resolution scales appropriate for their analysis. This hierarchical output structure preserves data locality and drastically reduces loading times for both global and regional studies (Becker et al., 2023).
- **Horizontal chunking and data access:** The dataset is chunked into tiles of manageable size, enabling targeted regional data retrieval without needing to load global files. This supports interactive and scalable diagnostics workflows (Becker et al., 2023).
- **Intake-enabled catalogs for remote access:** Output datasets are indexed via Intake catalogs (used with Intake-ESM), allowing users to access data on-demand using Python or CLI tools. Example notebooks available in `easy.gems` demonstrate how to query and load half-hourly, 3-hourly, and daily files efficiently.

High-resolution simulation datasets:

- **Cycle 2 Simulations:** **this is a comment** Cycle 2 marked a major advancement in model development within nextGEMS, focusing on improved ocean–atmosphere coupling, updated land-surface and cloud microphysics schemes, and stabilised configurations for long-duration coupled runs. It also introduced harmonised diagnostics and output protocols, enabling systematic evaluation and process-level comparisons between the ICON and IFS-FESOM models.

The Cycle 2 simulations included coupled storm-resolving runs at 5 km (ICON) and 4 km (IFS-FESOM) atmospheric resolution. These datasets are publicly available via the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ (Cycle 2 outputs of ICON (5 km) and IFS (4 km), DOI: [10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc2](https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc2) (Wieners et al., 2023)), and provide an important reference point for assessing the evolution of model performance in subsequent cycles.

- **Cycle 3 Simulations:** Cycle 3 represents the final development stage of the nextGEMS storm-resolving Earth system models before the production runs. Key improvements include refined coupling configurations, enhanced model stability, more realistic forcing setups, and increased consistency between ICON and IFS-FESOM simulations.

Simulations were conducted using ICON at 5 km resolution and IFS-FESOM with a 4 km atmospheric grid and 5 km ocean grid. Each simulation covers a continuous 5-year period, offering a unique high-resolution dataset for evaluating model performance and process interactions in coupled configurations over interannual timescales.

All Cycle 3 outputs are publicly available via the World Data Center for Climate (WDCC) at DKRZ (DOI: [10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3](https://doi.org/10.26050/WDCC/nextGEMS_cyc3) (Koldunov et al., 2023)).

- **Production Runs:** Building on the final configurations from Cycle 3, the nextGEMS project conducted multi-decadal production simulations using both the IFS-FESOM and ICON-Sapphire coupled storm-resolving models. These simulations span the period from 2020 to 2050, with an atmospheric resolution of approximately 9 km (IFS) and 10 km (ICON), coupled to a 5 km global ocean grid.

In addition to the future scenario simulations, a historical simulation using the IFS configuration was performed for the period 1990–2020, providing a high-resolution baseline for evaluating past climate conditions and model fidelity.

The production runs also include higher resolution simulations performed using ICON and IFS storm resolving models. In the case of ICON, a scenario simulation at 2.5 km resolution in atmosphere and ocean is performed for the time period from 2020 to 2023. Using IFS, two 2.8 km resolution (in both atmosphere and ocean) simulations are performed that integrate for 1 year from 2020-01-01 till 2021-03-01. One of the simulations has a reduced cloud base mass flux parameterization for deep convection, whereas the other simulation has no deep convective parameterization.

The complete set of production runs is accessible through the nextGEMS Intake catalog hosted by DKRZ. These production simulations add value to the project by delivering

decadal-resolution, coupled storm-resolving data at climate-relevant scales, enabling advanced diagnostics, hydrological and ecosystem applications, and input into climate policy frameworks.

Scientific publications:

The scientific output of nextGEMS includes over 30 peer-reviewed articles, preprints, and technical reports. These publications span model development, climate evaluation, and stakeholder co-design. Key publications include:

- **Model development and enhancements:**
 - Hohenegger et al., 2023 – “ICON-Sapphire: simulating the components of the Earth system and their interactions at kilometer and subkilometer scales”
 - Rackow et al., 2025 – “Multi-year simulations at kilometre scale with the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to FESOM2.5 and NEMOV3.4”
- **Evaluation and bias reduction:**
 - Nowak et al., 2025 – “A First Look at the Global Climatology of Low-Level Clouds in Storm Resolving Models”
 - Dolores-Tesillos et al., 2025 – “On the role of moist and dry processes in atmospheric blocking biases in the Euro-Atlantic region in CMIP6”
- **Stakeholder applications and co-production:**
 - Baulenas, Bojovic, et al., 2023 – “User Selection and Engagement for Climate Services Coproduction”
 - Baulenas, Versteeg, et al., 2023 – “Assembling the climate story: use of storyline approaches in climate-related science”
- **Technical documentation and model outputs:**
 - Wieners et al., 2023 – *nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 2 simulations for ICON and IFS*
 - Koldunov et al., 2023 – *nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 3 simulations for ICON and IFS*

A complete list of publications can be found in Appendix B and is available on Zenodo at:

<https://zenodo.org/communities/nextGEMS-publications>

2.2. Target Groups

The exploitation strategy of nextGEMS distinguishes between two categories of stakeholders based on their proximity to the project’s technical work and their capacity to directly use its

results:

- **Near-field communities**, who interacted closely with project activities and can directly exploit outputs such as models, data, and workflows.
- **Far-field communities**, who benefit indirectly through knowledge, evidence, and long-term capacity-building.

Near-Field Stakeholder Groups

These include the Earth-system Science Community, applied 'Users', and Technologists. They were actively engaged throughout the project and have the technical capacity to exploit the scientific and technical results directly.

Earth-system Science Community This group includes researchers developing and evaluating climate and Earth system models, ranging from core nextGEMS partners to the broader international modeling community. Their engagement was central to the project's scientific co-production approach.

- **Who is included:** Climate scientists and model developers at nextGEMS partner institutions (e.g., MPI-M, ECMWF, AWI), as well as external groups working on model development, evaluation, and intercomparison.
- **Engagement during nextGEMS:** All major scientific activities were carried out in close collaboration with this community. Participation extended beyond the consortium via open hackathons, fostering exchange on model diagnostics, workflows, and scientific questions. Many publications feature co-authorship from both project partners and external researchers.
- **Value derived from project results:** The community benefits from access to storm-resolving simulations and model innovations, shared via open repositories and scientific publications.
- **Post-project uptake:** Simulation data will remain accessible through institutional archives (e.g., DKRZ). Future model development and evaluation will continue through successor projects like *WarmWorld* and *TerraDT*.

Applied 'Users' Applied users include researchers and practitioners in energy, fisheries, and environmental applications who co-developed pilot studies and challenge problems with the nextGEMS team.

- **Who is included:** Institutions such as IBERDROLA, VESTAS Wind Systems, and marine scientists connected through TRIATLAS for example, as well as through the lasting collaboration between the project partner from Senegal and the fishery community from West Africa.
- **Engagement during nextGEMS:** Users co-designed science challenge problems for the

hackathons, with applications in renewable energy and marine productivity in the West African upwelling zone. During the energy storyline co-development process, a community of Spanish energy stakeholders - spanning representatives from the ministry, NGO, renewable and research sector - has been built and maintained throughout the project. Another example is participation of renewable energy sector representatives in nextGEMS hackathons, where they worked side-by-side with project scientists. Strong connections and links built are expected to last after the project ends. As one interviewed user from renewable energy sector said after the hackathon they attended: "A lot of information is obtained from informal interactions [in hackathon]. That [information] is not available in documentation."

- **Value derived from project results:** High-resolution simulations supported new analyses of wind and solar potential, ocean dynamics, and fisheries. Early involvement ensured the relevance of results to user needs. As confirmed by another hackathon participant from renewable energy: "I'll bring the attention [to nextGEMS results] in my organization. I'll present my findings [calculated at the hackathon]. People have questions about future climate effect on energy!"
- **Post-project continuation:** Collaborations and data access support ongoing application and analysis beyond the project's duration.

Technologists This group includes experts working on high-performance computing (HPC), model integration, data management, and AI-enhanced workflows. They play a crucial role in ensuring that storm-resolving Earth system modeling can scale efficiently and be integrated into next-generation computing environments.

- **Who is included:** Technologists from modeling centers (e.g., ECMWF, DKRZ), HPC institutions (e.g., BSC, Jülich, CSCS), and technology companies (e.g., NVIDIA, inception.AI). Many were involved as partners or collaborators through linked European projects and computing networks.
- **Engagement during nextGEMS:** Involved in workflow design, data handling, and machine learning integration.
- **Value derived from project results:** Tools and workflows developed on nextGEMS data enhanced reproducibility, scalability, and AI-readiness.
- **Post-project continuation:** Lessons and tools developed will be integrated into successor projects like *WarmWorld* or *TerraDT*, national HPC programs, and emerging AI-climate modeling partnerships.

Far-Field Stakeholder Groups

These include the Broader User Community, Policy Makers, and the General Public. Their exploitation of results is typically indirect but strategically important.

Broader User Community Practitioners and scientists in applied fields (e.g., agriculture, hydrology, urban planning) may adopt insights or data products from nextGEMS.

- **Engagement:** Broader User Community was not directly involved in development, but served through pre-processed datasets and accessible explanatory materials, such as science explainers, animated visualisations, and short videos aimed at making key model findings understandable for non-specialists.
- **Future exploitation:** High-resolution data supports sectoral modeling and integrated assessments across Europe and beyond.

Policy Makers European and regional African policy actors were engaged to ensure that high-resolution climate knowledge informs policy processes.

- **Engagement:** Two policy briefs were developed to support science-informed policymaking:
 - *Reaching the Last Mile with km-Scale Earth System Models* – addressing the integration of high-resolution models into European Earth system modelling strategy.
 - *The Impact of Hackathons for km-Scale Earth System Modelling* – highlighting the role of hackathons in fostering innovation and stakeholder engagement.

The primary target audience of both briefs is European policy-makers. Additional engagement took place with regional actors in West Africa through workshops and stakeholder dialogue.

- **Post-project impact:** A representative of nextGEMS will participate in a European Commission policy event shortly after the project ends, alongside other European Earth system modelling initiatives. This event will provide an opportunity to present key findings relevant to policy, foster exchange between projects, and contribute to shaping the future research and innovation agenda.

General Public and Media nextGEMS used science communication to improve public understanding of high-resolution Earth system modeling.

- **Channels:** The project developed videos, blog posts, social media content, animations, and interviews to explain the science behind nextGEMS and the significance of its outputs. Media outreach was strengthened through strategic dissemination via platforms such as the German science communication network *Informationsdienst Wissenschaft (idw)*, enabling wider visibility of selected content among journalists and the broader public. Additionally, the project produced science art outputs—three annual calendars under the *nextCalendArt* initiative and a set of *nextScienceArt Postcards*—featuring model-based visualizations with aesthetic and educational value. These materials were disseminated online and at events to foster broader appreciation of the project's outcomes.
- **Long-term value:** All communication materials remain publicly accessible and can be used for educational, outreach, and engagement purposes beyond the project duration.

2.3. Exploitation Measures

Integration into Successor Projects

A key pathway for exploiting the results of nextGEMS is their uptake in successor projects, ensuring continuity of development and broader use. The models, workflows, and community structures built in nextGEMS are already being integrated into ongoing research funded under Horizon Europe and national programs.

- The Horizon Europe project **WarmWorld** builds directly on the scientific and technical foundation laid by nextGEMS. It continues the development of storm-resolving Earth system models, further refines diagnostics, and expands the modelled processes and applications.
- The project **TerraDT** (Terra Digital Twin), part of the European Destination Earth (DestinE) initiative, is expected to further exploit nextGEMS results by integrating storm-resolving simulations into digital twin applications. The model and data infrastructure developed in nextGEMS provides a technical and scientific basis for this transition.
- **Simulation data and workflows** from nextGEMS are made available to other projects for physical diagnostics, machine learning applications, and process studies. Tools and scripts developed during the project have been adopted as starting points for new production runs.
- The **collaborative structures and community formats** developed in nextGEMS — including open hackathons, science challenge problems, and knowledge co-production — have proven effective and scalable. These formats have been adopted beyond the project, most notably in the [WCRP Digital Earths Global Hackathon \(2025\)](#), which applied the nextGEMS hackathon model to a wider international research community. This demonstrates the potential of nextGEMS methods to shape future collaboration across Earth system science initiatives.

These institutional activities demonstrate that nextGEMS results are not limited to academic impact but are being translated into improved tools and infrastructures across Europe.

Institutional Uptake and Operational Use

Key institutions involved in nextGEMS — including major modeling centers and HPC facilities — have already begun integrating project results into their operational and strategic activities. This form of uptake ensures the long-term relevance and application of nextGEMS developments beyond the research context.

The following is a selected overview of institutional uptake from a subset of project partners. A complete list of exploitation activities and follow-up plans is provided in the appendix A.

- **ECMWF** has integrated developments from nextGEMS into its operational forecast system and is continuing this work in Horizon Europe projects like TerraDT and EERIE. Its storm-

and eddy-resolving IFS-based modeling forms the foundation of the Climate Adaptation Digital Twin in Destination Earth.

- **MPI-M** is incorporating nextGEMS insights into ongoing ICON development, including high-resolution simulations and model evaluation in projects like WarmWorld. Secured computing time and upcoming proposals support continued use and advancement of nextGEMS approaches.
- **BSC** is maintaining stakeholder relationships initiated in nextGEMS, particularly in the energy and fishery sectors. Lessons from stakeholder co-creation processes are informing follow-up activities, such as within the Spanish national project BOREAS.
- **DTU** has applied nextGEMS output in the education and training of young researchers, particularly in master and PhD programs focused on ocean–atmosphere interactions. This contributes to capacity building and long-term scientific uptake.

Training and Capacity Building

Training and capacity building were central components of nextGEMS, both as a means of exploiting project outputs and as a strategy to build expertise for the post-project era. The project's simulation data, modeling tools, and workflows were integrated into educational activities at multiple levels, from early-career researcher training to high-level professional development.

- The project organized a series of **international hackathons**, which served as immersive training environments for participants from within and beyond the consortium. These events supported hands-on learning in working with storm-resolving model output, diagnostics tools, and cloud-based workflows.
- The **WCRP Global Hackathon** in 2025 was modeled on the nextGEMS hackathon format and provided many new participants access to high-resolution climate simulations. Workflows and tools developed in nextGEMS—such as Intake catalogs and Healpix-based output format—were adapted and reused at other institutions and for other models, promoting a shared infrastructure for analyzing km-scale simulations.
- The **science explainers** created by nextGEMS have been included in the education resource database curated by the Horizon Europe project ESM2025, providing long-term visibility and accessibility (<https://www.esm2025.eu/education-and-professional-development/resources/education-resources-from-eu-research-projects/>).
- Several partner institutions used nextGEMS outputs in **graduate-level teaching**. Master's students at MISU conducted thesis work using nextGEMS simulation data. UCM held a **Student Hackathon** for analyzing simulation output.

Outreach and Strategic Communication

While dissemination was formally addressed in a separate task, selected outreach and strategic communication activities in nextGEMS also contributed to exploitation — especially where they enhanced visibility, stakeholder engagement, and long-term uptake of project results.

- A series of videos and blog posts were developed to explain complex topics such as climate extremes, convection, and model development. These materials supported not only dissemination but also served as entry points for broader community use of the data and methods.
- **Social media communication** through platforms such as LinkedIn and Twitter helped establish a project identity within the wider research and policy landscape, reaching audiences beyond the scientific core.
- The project was an active member of the **#ClimateResearchNet** communication network, coordinated by ESM2025, which amplified strategic messages and facilitated cross-project visibility within Horizon Europe.

2.4. Exploitation Pathways

This section brings together the different exploitation pathways by linking each of the project's key results to the six identified target groups. Table 2.4 illustrates how each group engages with and benefits from the three main results of *nextGEMS*.

Together, these pathways demonstrate how *nextGEMS* outputs are actively exploited across scientific, institutional, and public domains. The integration of open data, co-developed tools, and educational materials into diverse contexts ensures that the project's legacy will extend well beyond its formal conclusion. Through targeted engagement and strategic reuse, *nextGEMS* has helped shape the future of storm-resolving Earth system modeling and its role in science, society, and policy.

Table 3: Overview of how *nextGEMS* results are exploited across target groups.

Target Group	Key result: ESM Development	Key result: Simulation Outputs	Key result: Publications and Methods
Earth-system Science Community	Access to new storm-resolving models (ICON, IFS); involved in development and diagnostics via hackathons and open tools.	Used for process evaluation, intercomparison, and development of new diagnostics. Available via WDCC and Intake catalog.	Authorship and use in peer-reviewed studies; basis for continued research and development.
Applied Users (Energy, Fisheries)	Co-design of challenge problems with modeling relevance; involvement of industry and applied partners.	High-res simulations support energy and marine productivity applications. Used in pilot studies and thesis work.	Cited in use-case driven papers.
Technologists	Development of workflows and HPC optimization strategies (e.g., chunking, HEALPix, intake catalogs).	Testing data transfer, workflow performance, and AI-integration capabilities.	Methods and tools shared with community; used in successor projects like TerraDT.
Broader User Community	Tools and documentation facilitate later adaptation by practitioners in agriculture, hydrology, etc.	Access to simplified products; integration into downstream applications and education.	Used in outreach and explainers.
Policy Makers	Support for Digital Twin strategy and DestinE development through institutional uptake.	Data for informing policy briefs on climate change.	Results synthesized in policy brief on climate simulations with km-scale earth system models.
General Public and Media	Highlighted in science explainers and outreach materials to illustrate climate model progress.	Visual content and narratives used in media and education; part of ClimateResearchNet communication network.	Accessible summaries and video explainers increase understanding of storm-resolving models.

3. Post-project Sustainability and Continuation Plan

3.1. Governance and Community Continuity

To ensure the long-term impact of nextGEMS, the project has established a foundation for sustained collaboration beyond its formal conclusion. An informal consortium of key modelling centres and partners—including MPI-M, ECMWF, DKRZ, AWI, and others—will maintain cooperation through coordinated proposal development. This lightweight governance structure supports the continued evolution and use of the nextGEMS tools, workflows, and simulations within the broader Earth system modelling community.

The dedicated nextGEMS community space on Mattermost will continue to facilitate:

- Maintenance and development of the ICON and IFS-FESOM model branches;
- Preservation and sharing of simulation configurations, diagnostics, and analysis workflows;
- Coordination of scientific priorities.

Importantly, the successful **WCRP Global Hackathon**, which followed the nextGEMS hackathon format, demonstrated the scalability and relevance of this collaborative engagement model. Building on this momentum, nextGEMS partners plan to continue organising **annual hackathons** in the coming years. These activities will serve as vital meeting points for the extended modelling community, supporting knowledge exchange, joint development, and fostering the next generation of Earth system scientists.

3.2. Digital Infrastructure and Knowledge Preservation

Long-term access to project results is a cornerstone of nextGEMS' sustainability plan:

- The project website (www.nextgems-h2020.eu) will remain active for at least five years after the project ends, hosted by MPI-M. It will continue to serve as a central hub for documentation, data links, model tutorials, and outreach content.
- All public deliverables, reports, and publications are archived with persistent DOIs in the **nextGEMS Zenodo community** (zenodo.org/communities/nextgems-publications), ensuring open and citable access.
- Simulation output, particularly from Cycles 2 and 3, is archived through the **WDCC at DKRZ**. For NextGEMS production simulations performed with ICON and IFS, the corresponding data catalog is archived at WDCC. Further, output from WP6 is also archived at WDCC. Archived datasets can be browsed¹. Those datasets are assigned a DOI, are available under CC-BY 4.0 license and a corresponding citation information is provided on the landing pages of the datasets. All other simulation datasets produced in NextGEMS

¹<https://www.wdc-climate.de/ui/project?acronym=nextGEMS>

are documented on [easy.GEMS²](https://easy.gems.dkcz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/simulation_overview.html) and are available for reuse under CC-BY 4.0 license. Until complete citation information is provided on [easy.GEMS](https://easy.gems.dkcz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/simulation_overview.html), those simulations are to be cited as Segura et al. (2025)³.

- After the end of the project, preservation of NextGEMS data will transition into operational data management tasks at DKRZ, ensuring the continued availability of NextGEMS simulation output for the community under the conditions of best use of available data centre resources for the benefit of all users.

3.3. Funding and Resource Strategies

Progress achieved within nextGEMS is underpinning an ecosystem of ongoing and developing European projects. Particularly as interest in the hydrological cycle and extremes increases the capabilities demonstrated within nextGEMS are in increasing demand. This includes:

- Follow-up proposals under **Horizon Europe** (three pending proposals), and national funding schemes (e.g., BMBF, CNRS), notably the second four year phase of WarmWorld, are being prepared by consortium members.
- The demonstration of model capability and scaling supports compute time proposals on **EuroHPC**, **PRACE**, and national super-computing facilities which is enabling high-resolution simulations and model testing for the broader community..
- The **Destination Earth** programme is an outgrowth and exploitation of the nextGEMS models. It offers a direct and tangible path for nextGEMS tools and outputs to be used in climate digital twins, ensuring ongoing EU-level support and alignment with policy-driven digital infrastructure, and also offers funding opportunities for further continuing the nextGEMS line of model development.

3.4. Integration with European and Global Initiatives

nextGEMS outputs are a centerpiece of the World Climate Research Programmes Lighthouse Activity on Digital Earths, the modeling capability is intergrated closely with the most advanced ESA Earth Explorer mission (EarthCARE) through the ECOMIP initiative, and it will be featured a the global km-scale summit being organized by WarmWorld in 2026. Specifically:

- The technical and scientific infrastructure of nextGEMS will continue to underpin **Destination Earth's Climate Digital Twin** and the **Digital Twin Engine (DTE)** through the support of base funding by the partner institutes and developing national and international projects.
- nextGEMS will support coordinated initiatives in the framework of the **WCRP Lighthouse**

²https://easy.gems.dkcz.de/DYAMOND/NextGEMS/simulation_overview.html

³Segura, H., et al.: nextGEMS: entering the era of kilometer-scale Earth system modeling, EGU sphere [preprint], <https://doi.org/10.5194/egusphere-2025-509>, 2025

Activities. The most immediate of these is ECOMIP, the EarthCARE model intercomparison project.

4. Conclusion

nextGEMS has delivered three key results: storm-resolving Earth system model development, high-resolution simulation datasets, and a large body of scientific publications. These results are already being exploited by a wide range of target groups, from model developers and applied researchers to policy actors and the general public.

Project outputs are reused in successor projects like *WarmWorld* and *TerraDT*, institutional workflows at ECMWF and MPI-M, and broader educational and communication efforts. The simulation data is openly accessible, and the community formats developed—such as hackathons and challenge problems—have proven effective and are now adopted in other contexts, including the WCRP Digital Earths Hackathon. Other, informal links built during the project, such as the ones with the international and Spanish renewable energy community or with the interdisciplinary ECR community, are expected to continue supporting collaboration within these communities as well as between these and the ESM community.

Together, these measures ensure that *nextGEMS* results remain visible, accessible, and useful beyond the end of the project.

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A. Exploitation Activities by Project Partner

Partner: Barcelona Supercomputing Center (BSC)

Key Contributions:

Stakeholder engagement

Exploitation Activities: Engagement with different stakeholder groups helped build a community of nextGEMS users and collaborators. In this sense we had a role of brokering nextGEMS knowledge to these different communities, such as energy and fishery, as well as facilitating communication from these communities to nextGEMS scientists with the idea to shape the scientific progress and final outcome into more robust and useful information. Some of these activities and co-created knowledge are reported in the academic publications (see at the bottom). Other engagement activities, such as engagement with scientists to co-create science explainers have a form of communication materials available to broader stakeholder community. A third example is engagement with regional policy makers in Africa and policy briefs aimed to inform EC policy makers.

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Users (from the energy and fishery sectors) with storyline co-creation workshop and follow up activities; policy-makers through engagement activities in West Africa and policy briefs for European policymakers; Earth-system science and broader user community with science explainers.

Follow-up Plans:

We plan to maintain established relationships with users communities. One example is the Spanish national project BOREAS where we will continue engaging with the national energy stakeholders.

Related Outputs:

- [Baulenas & Bojovic \(2023\)](#) – Co-Producing Storylines for Resilient Energy Scenarios
- Baulenas et al (submitted) Km-scale earth system models to support the renewable energy transition: combining storyline approaches as boundary object

Partner: Technical University of Denmark (DTU)

Key Contributions:

Model development and scientific analysis

Exploitation Activities: We will use our Bayesian optimizer to improve precipitation simulations

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Students and scientific community

Follow-up Plans:

We will use the optimizer below for the upcoming EU call on better ESMs

Related Outputs:

- [Mrozowska et al. \(2025\)](#) – Fast and efficient: Bayesian optimization with GPU acceleration for ocean models

Partner: European Centre for Medium-Range Weather Forecasts (ECMWF)

Key Contributions:

Model development, data production, scientific analysis, user support.

Exploitation Activities: Academic publications (Rackow et al., 2025; Segura et al., 2025)

Incorporation of some model developments to ECMWF's operational model version

Uptake of nextGEMS developments (models, ways of working, scientific analysis workflows, etc) into other Horizon projects like TerraDT or EERIE, and into the EU strategic initiative Destination Earth, in particular into the Climate Change Adaptation Digital Twin: the storm-and-eddy resolving models pioneered in nextGEMS form the substrate of DestinE's Climate DT which is aiming to operationalize for the first time climate projections.

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Stakeholders (climate service providers, scientific community, policy-makers), both via nextGEMS simulations as well as via simulations provided via Destination Earth.

Follow-up Plans:

The natural continuation of the IFS-based and ICON models developed in nextGEMS relies on the operationalization of those km-scale climate models within Destination Earth, as well as on further development of its components in Horizon projects such as TerraDT, and uptake of relevant developments in ECMWF operational forecasting system

Related Outputs: Publications:

- Rackow et al., 2025 – “Multi-year simulations at kilometre scale with the Integrated Forecasting System coupled to FESOM2.5 and NEMOv3.4”
- Segura et al., 2025 – “nextGEMS: entering the era of kilometer-scale Earth system modeling”
- Takasuka et al., 2025 – “Precipitation Characteristics and Thermodynamic-Convection Coupling in Global Kilometer-Scale Simulations”

Datasets:

- Wieners et al., 2024 – *nextGEMS: output of the production simulations for ICON and IFS*

- Koldunov et al., 2023 – *nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 3 simulations for ICON and IFS*
- Wieners et al., 2023 – *nextGEMS: output of the model development cycle 2 simulations for ICON and IFS*

Partner: Karlsruhe Institute of Technology (KIT)

Key Contributions:

Implementation of advanced dust emission schemes into ICON-HAM-lite

Analysis of the impacts/benefits of storm-resolving modeling on dust generation and transport, e.g. in a continental-scale dust storm.

Exploitation Activities:

- Publication on tracking algorithm for haboob dust storms
- Publication on global haboob characteristics based on ICON-HAM-lite
- Publication of new dust emission schemes in ICON-HAM-lite
- Participation in ECOMIP

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Scientific community.

Follow-up Plans:

We will definitely continue doing storm-resolving modeling, e.g. in the context of ECOMIP, but also in other contexts.

Partner: Stockholm University (MISU)

Key Contributions:

Mainly scientific analysis and to some extent model development and also data production

Exploitation Activities: Main means of output is scientific publications, and we've also been able to use nextGEMS for training and education having eg MSc students work on data, and students, postdocs, seniors participating in hackathons. We have and will continue to integrate nextGEMS into other projects, as eg. graduate students or postdocs funded by other projects also working on nextGEMS data.

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Scientific community and students; also some stake holder influence at the last hackathon when we had several renewable energy people joining and contributing, and co-producing knowledge.

Follow-up Plans:

Group members continue working with nextGEMS data

Related Outputs:

None yet available.

Partner: Max Planck Institute for Meteorology (MPI-M)

MPI-M was involved in two of the nextGEMS themes (Storms & Land and Storms & Ocean). The information is therefore given for both themes separately.

Key Contributions:

Storms & Land:

- Model development and validation of the climate over land.
- Scientific analysis supporting ICON development and evaluation.

Storms & Ocean:

- Development and analysis of model experiments to improve the representation of upper ocean mixing, including both stand-alone ocean and coupled simulations.
- Analysis of intra-annual variability in the tropical Atlantic (e.g., Tropical Instability Waves and near-inertial waves), in collaboration with GEOMAR and UCPH.
- Provided ocean biogeochemistry enabled ICON simulations for partners investigating fisheries and air–sea CO₂ exchange in relation to mesoscale features.

Exploitation Activities:

Storms & Land:

- Improvement of the ICON model version.
- Scientific publications based on project results.

Storms & Ocean:

- Sensitivity experiments used for guiding model development, shared via easy.gems.
- nextGEMS work regarding ocean mixing has been conducted in collaboration with activities in the German DFG-funded program TRR 181 “Energy exchanges”
- Use of nextGEMS experiments in Master’s and ongoing academic projects (e.g., coral reef studies in the Caribbean).

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Storms & Land:

Scientific community, teaching, outreach.

Storms & Ocean:

- Results and the nextGEMS experiments will be beneficial for the scientific community as there is strong interest to study small-scale processes in the ocean and at the ocean-atmosphere interface. Operational centers may benefit from model improvement and better process understanding.
- The km-scale-resolution model experiments offer a huge variety of novel approaches for Master-thesis and PhD topics.
- We have reached out to the larger scientific community interested in the role of ocean eddies (e.g. the H2020 EERIE project) by linking our workshop and hackathon activities.
- The link to stakeholders was realized by the S&O team successfully with regard to the fishery-research community.

Follow-up Plans:

Storms & Land:

- Secured computing time on Jupyter to conduct a 1-year simulation at a grid spacing of 1.25 km.
- Horizon Europe follow-up proposal on climate extremes.
- Secured funding from the German Science Foundation for a 7-year project on stability and surprises in the natural dynamics.
- Involvement in WarmWorld 2.

Storms & Ocean:

- Ongoing high-resolution ocean modeling in the EU EPOC project (e.g., AMOC-focused ICON configurations). EPOC benefits directly from the nextGEMS model development.

Related Outputs:

- Bastin et al., 2025 – “Sensitivity of the tropical Atlantic to vertical mixing in two ocean models (ICON-O v2.6.6 and FESOM v2.5)”
- Specht et al., 2024 – “Seasonality of Subsurface Shear Instabilities at Tropical Instability Wave Fronts in the Atlantic Ocean in a High-Resolution Simulation”
- Lee and Hohenegger, 2024 – “Weaker land–atmosphere coupling in global storm-resolving simulation”

Partner: Universidad Complutense de Madrid (UCM)

Key Contributions:

Scientific analysis

Exploitation Activities:

During the project:

- Integration into other projects. Specifically, we are using analyses of nextGEMS simulations in national projects DISTROPIA and OFF (references PID2021-125806NB-I00 and TED2021-130106B-I00).
- We're also working on three academic publications we hope will be submitted around the end of the project. They are focused on the representation and projection of rainfall in the West African monsoon, the variability of the equatorial Atlantic, and on the representation and projection of snow over the Iberian mountain ranges. During the project, we have also presented results from the simulations in International forums (EGU, Oceans' Science Meeting...).
- We've used nextGEMS simulation for training and education purposes in the framework of the Master's in Meteorology and Geophysics of the Complutense University of Madrid. Results from the simulations have been analysed in the framework of the subject "Meteorological Data Analysis", several Master's Theses, and extracurricular practice (the Madrid Hackathon held in 2022 where the students analysed data from cycle 1 dpp0066 simulation). Results from students' analyses have also been shown in a National meeting (XIII assembly of the Spanish Climatological Association held in El Escorial, Madrid, 22-24 January 2025: <https://aeclim.org/xiii-congreso-internacional-aec/>). In addition, several students from this Master's have received stipends and have collaborated in nextGEMS Hackathons, which provided further training for them. At the PhD level, nextGEMS simulations and Hackathons have also served for the training of PhD students in the group. At least 6 of our PhD students have benefited in varying degrees from this training.

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

The scientific community and students, mainly.

Follow-up Plans:

After the project ends, we plan to exploit nextGEMS simulations and related ones (like those in DestinE) for future potential projects and related academic publications. We will continue to use the simulated data for training and education, not only at the Master's level but also at the undergraduate level. We have already agreed with an undergraduate student to train him through the analysis of DestinE storyline simulations during the next semester.

Funding proposals have been submitted which exploit nextGEMS simulations and related ones.

Related Outputs:

None yet available.

Partner: University of Helsinki (UH)

Key Contributions:

Model development (Algorithmic tuning methods)

Scientific analysis (Development and demonstration of observation-based verification methods)

Exploitation Activities:

During the project:

- The power of algorithmic model tuning was demonstrated with 20 key parameters of OpenIFS in weather forecasting mode.
- The new observation-based verification metric Filter Likelihood Score was used to expose that improved deterministic forecast skill does not necessarily imply improved ensemble forecasts.

After the project:

- Transition from algorithmic tuning of weather forecasts to algorithmic tuning of climate models.
- Algorithmic tuning of coupled models.

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Weather and climate modelling communities; operational forecast centres

Follow-up Plans:

Follow-up work funded by Academy of Finland.

Related Outputs:

- Tuppi et al., 2023 – “Simultaneous Optimization of 20 Key Parameters of the Integrated Forecasting System of ECMWF Using OpenIFS. Part I: Effect on Deterministic Forecasts”
- Ekblom et al., 2023 – “Filter Likelihood as an Observation-Based Verification Metric in Ensemble Forecasting”

Partner: University of Hamburg (UHH)

Key Contributions:

Scientific analysis, model development (through model evaluation).

Exploitation Activities: Publications, integration in other projects (through model evaluation).

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Scientific community, stakeholders via model assessment.

Follow-up Plans:

Additional publication (tentative title "Simulating shallow mesoscale overturning circulations in the trades with kilometer-scale Earth system models", by Ian Dragaud et al.)

Related Outputs:

- Nowak et al., 2025 – "A First Look at the Global Climatology of Low-Level Clouds in Storm Resolving Models"

Partner: University of Oxford (UOXF)

Key Contributions:

The development of the reduced complexity aerosol model ICON-HAM-lite suitable for global km-scale modelling and its application to study aerosol effects on clouds and climate.

Exploitation Activities: We are already actively working with ICON-HAM-lite in the EC project CleanCloud and hope to do so in EC projects currently being proposed.

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Scientific community: open source model, publications

Follow-up Plans:

Continued involvement through CleanCloud and future EU proposals.

Related Outputs:

- Weiss et al., 2025 – "ICON-HAM-lite 1.0: simulating the Earth system with interactive aerosols at kilometer scales"

Partner: University of Warsaw

Key Contributions:

- Analyzed the representation of tropical and subtropical low-level shallow clouds in the nextGEMS models.
- Investigated ways to improve the representation of stratocumulus clouds in storm-resolving models by implementing an anisotropic model of sub-grid scale turbulence.
- Explored potential modifications to the collision-coalescence algorithm used in particle-based microphysics schemes to enhance their suitability for storm-resolving models

Exploitation Activities:

The results from the nextGEMS models were used in academic publications. The experience

gained in working with this data during the project will also be applied in future research and publications.

Target Users / Beneficiaries:

Scientific community

Follow-up Plans:

The University of Warsaw Lagrangian Cloud Model (UWLCM), our large-eddy simulation model, was utilized and further developed during the project. Its development will continue under the EuroHPC Hanami project.

Related Outputs:

- Nowak et al., 2025 – “A First Look at the Global Climatology of Low-Level Clouds in Storm Resolving Models”
- Morrison et al., 2024 – “Impacts of stochastic coalescence variability on warm rain initiation using Lagrangian microphysics in box and large-eddy simulations”
- Segura et al., 2025 – “nextGEMS: entering the era of kilometer-scale Earth system modeling”
- [UWLCM GitHub repository](#)

B. nextGEMS publications

nextGEMS Publication List

Authors: The nextGEMS community
July 2025

The research leading to these results has received funding from the European Union's Horizon 2020 Research and Innovation programmes under grant agreement No 101003470

Peer reviewed publications

2022

- Beech, N., T. Rackow, T. Semmler, S. Danilov, Q. Wang, and T. Jung (2022). “Long-term evolution of ocean eddy activity in a warming world”. In: *Nature Climate Change* 12.10, pp. 910–917. DOI: 10.1038/s41558-022-01478-3.
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